

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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MEASURES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The article examines the current state of tourism infrastructure in the regions of Uzbekistan, the author's definition of independent tourism, scientifically substantiated the factors influencing the development of independent tourism, analyzed the strengths and weaknesses of the tourist infrastructure of the country, based on the reviews of foreign tourists left on specialized travel websites and social networks, identified the results to be achieved by developing tourism infrastructure in little known regions of the country.

Key words: solo tourism, infrastructure, mobile technology, factors affecting independent tourism, electronic booking platforms.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada O'zbekiston hududlarida turizm infratuzilmasining hozirgi holati ko'rib chiqiladi, muallif tomonidan mustaqil turizm tushunchasiga berilgan ta'rif, mustaqil turizmning rivojlanishiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar ilmiy asoslab berilgan, mamlakatimiz turistik infratuzilmasining kuchli va zaif tomonlari tahlil qilingan. Ixtisoslashtirilgan sayyohlik veb-saytlari va ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda qoldirgan xorijlik sayyohlarning sharhlari mamlakatimizning kam ma'lum bo'lgan hududlarida turizm infratuzilmasini rivojlantirish orqali erishiladigan natijalarni belgilab beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: yakka turizm, infratuzilma, mobil texnologiyalar, mustaqil turizmga ta'sir etuvchi omillar, elektron bronlash platformalari.

Аннотация: В статье рассмотрено современное состояние туристической инфраструктуры в регионах Узбекистана, дано авторское определение независимого туризма, научно обоснованы факторы, влияющие на развитие независимого туризма, проанализированы сильные и слабые стороны туристской инфраструктуры страны, на основе Отзывов иностранных туристов, оставленные на специализированных туристических сайтах и в социальных сетях, определили результаты, которых необходимо достичь за счет развития туристической инфраструктуры в малоизвестных регионах страны.

Ключевые слова: индивидуальный туризм, инфраструктура, мобильные технологии, факторы, влияющие на независимый туризм, платформы электронного бронирования.

INTRODUCTION

Uzbekistan is a country widely known in the world for its historical and cultural tourism. Its rich history, centuries-old ancient monuments, buildings and structures, mosques and mausoleums, houses, historical and religious figures are an example of this. Foreign tourists have been visiting our country continuously for many years. But it is difficult to say that the number of tourists is increasing significantly from year to year. In addition to the infrastructures listed above, the country of Uzbekistan expresses the need to develop such infrastructures as mountains, deserts, rivers, seas and forests, which are considered important for the category of independent travelers, and the sustainable development of tourism in the country. It is this situation that encourages the country's attractiveness and diversity of travel types to attract more independent travelers.

Weak infrastructure greatly hinders the development of the above directions in tourism. Based on this, the main problem of the research determines the need to conduct additional research on the development of convenient infrastructure for independent travelers in the country. The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the country's infrastructure, No. 559 of 17.09.2020 [1] on additional measures to «develop tourism infrastructure in mountainous areas» to further develop the tourist potential of the regions

and increasing efficiency, improving the system of attracting foreign investments and building additional jobs in remote areas, modern international all-season resorts, hotel complexes, cultural-health, trade-entertainment and other touristic facilities, the country's mountain a decision was made in order to create favorable conditions for the construction of modern engineering infrastructure in the regions.

For this reason, in order to sustainably develop the tourism sector in the country and increase its share in the national economy, to create organizational, economic and legal conditions for increasing the flow of the category of independent travelers, to make more effective use of the country's tourist areas with great potential, and to have a direct impact on it. internal and external factors, development of economic sectors (banking systems, money exchange offices, etc.), organization of infrastructure for tourists who prefer to plan independent trips and the need to show a new image of the country due to its promotion in the world tourism market is being born.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

In the course of the research, the opinions and comments expressed by international and national scientists on the tourism infrastructure were analyzed. In particular, from Indonesian scientists A.R.Hafnidar, M.Affuddin and Harry Akbar in their researches stated that infrastructure becomes the main device in the development of the tourism industry and studied problems such as determining the priority level of tourism infrastructure development and developing the priority direction of potential investments in the country [2].

A.V. Kormisheva, in her article published in the «Innovation and Investment» magazine, emphasized the development of basic infrastructures such as communication tools, presentation of tourist objects, accommodation and accommodation facilities, trade, household and treatment-prophylactic services, sports facilities in the development of the tourism industry. According to the research results of M.S.Oboronin, independent travelers have discovered many infrastructure-related shortcomings during their travels. In his opinion, information services for independent travelers, taking into account the fact that independent travelers in most cases move in their own vehicles, the lack of road signs on the roads, and the inability of internet platforms that book services online to provide accurate and correct information found a solution to the problems [3].

In his article, Q. H. Nguyen focused on three main components in attracting more independent travelers in the country of Vietnam, emphasizing the effectiveness of attracting foreign investment in the development of transport and communication infrastructure, restaurants and hotels, and entertainment infrastructure. tgan [4]. Scientists such as D.Y.Dalimunthe, Devi Valeriani, Fitra Hartini, Rulyanti Wardhani, in their article on the sustainable development of tourism through infrastructure development, studied 3 different types of economic, social and ecological infrastructure of Bangka Belitung Islands Province, based on the level of interest and level of foreign tourists during the tour. they emphasized their assessment on these 3 concepts [5].

Scholars such as Guodong Yan, Lin Zou, Yunan Liu, and Ruxue Ji have pointed out in their research that China's new infrastructure construction mainly includes information infrastructure, convergent infrastructure, and innovation infrastructure. He concluded that the development of tourism based on information and network infrastructures can better reflect the diversity of regional conditions, and the construction of new infrastructures will make knowledge and information the main production factors of the digital economy [6]. B.Turayev, U.Atamurodov defined in their studies that «Tourist infrastructure is a set of objects with material and immaterial properties aimed at qualitatively satisfying various wishes of tourists in a certain time and place» [7]. In the research work of all the above-mentioned scientists, the infrastructure necessary for independent travelers in the field of tourism has not been sufficiently studied. They focused on comprehensive tourism infrastructure.

In our opinion, independent tourism is a form of independent formation of one's own tourist destinations, independent management, self-service and management of travel processes. Foreign experience shows that the main objective factor that influenced the rapid development of independent tourism was the introduction of digital and information technologies and telecommunications. Technology is at the heart of reservation systems. Thanks to technology, travelers have access to the Internet and through this they have the opportunity to get information about all kinds of services, including tour packages, accommodation, air and rail services, and car rentals. Previously, all the main services were provided by the travel agency, but now they are in «online» mode travelers are finding solutions along the way. For example, it became possible to choose products and individual services, make a reservation, pay for services in advance, cancel a reservation or rebook. There is a need to further develop the internet speed and information technologies, which are one of the weak points of the country.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the course of the research, research on international and national opportunities for the development of independent tourism was studied. In the process of forming the article, methods such as scientific hypotheses, comparative analysis, observation and sampling, statistical and dynamic approach, and content analysis were used.

Analysis and results Tourism infrastructure is the main link of tourism development, it helps the development of the territory and the rational use of tourism infrastructure resources, providing services to tourists, creating necessary and sufficient comfort in their places of residence. At the same time, the development of tourism leads to the improvement of the living conditions of the local population, for example, to the employment of the residents of the region. Tourism infrastructure broadly includes accommodation, event venues, parks, dining and entertainment venues, cultural and artistic facilities, transportation networks, interchanges, aviation, marine, tourist destinations. including roads etc.

Airports are the first impression a traveler makes of a destination. For this reason, establishing solid air connections is very important for increasing the flow of travelers and diversifying tourism. Road networks and transport system ensure movement within the country. All accommodations allow tourists to relax after a hard excursion, while restaurants allow foreign tourists to taste national food and stay refreshed during the tour.

The above image shows the basic and additional services required for the trip. These tourist services are the main component needed during the trip, and play an important role in attracting travelers, increasing the attractiveness of the travel destination, and meeting the needs of tourists. The main part of these tourist services are services belonging to the category of organized tourist groups. They mainly use tour products organized by tourist agencies. But only some of these service are used by independent travelers during their travels. This is because independent travelers have different travel needs than organized group travelers. Independent travelers plan their itineraries based on their budgets, and they look for non-traditional tourism services. For example, hitchhiking is free transportation between cities and countries. Independent travelers are mostly organized individually or in small groups. For this reason, budget travelers often use hitchhiking services.

Tourists belonging to the category of independent tourism usually travel alone, in pairs or in small, close groups of friends or family. They can range in age from millennials or Generation Y to retirees, and their incomes are generally higher than average, allowing them to travel independently, which can be more expensive than traveling with an organized group. But what all independent travelers have in common is that they avoid mass travel. In general, they want to explore the destinations of their choice independently and at their own pace, while focusing on enjoying the local cuisine, architecture, history and culture as much as possible [8].

The desire to travel independently is growing among travelers, especially after the pandemic. Independent travelers return 3 or more times a year and make up 11% of the total travel market. Independent travel has been on the rise since 2016, with a 761% increase in Google searches for «solo travel» in 2021. Women are the leaders in independent travel, accounting for 84% of the total travel market. According to Booking.com, the category belonging to the «Baby Boomer» generation currently has the highest rate of independent travel. In 2019, 40 percent of people aged 55 to 64 traveled alone. The largest increase in independent travel in 2022 was among women age 65 and older, rising from 4 percent overall in 2019 to 18 percent in 2022 [9].

As a result of the conducted research, several factors affecting the development of the independent tourism category were developed and they are shown in the following figure (Figure 2). Along with the development of the independent tourism category, the tourist attractiveness of the country, the diversification of services, serves as a driver for increasing the capacity of organizations operating in tourism. Young people who prefer to independently book accommodation, air and railway tickets and plan their route well are making a great contribution to changing the industry, i.e. to the development of this category.

In our opinion, this development is related to the popularization of modern technologies among the younger generation, now almost everyone has a personal smartphone, and such smartphones are not only a means of communication, but also perform many other functions, including tourism reservation of private services as well. In addition, the use of gadgets is also becoming popular among the older generation, and in the near future, we will be able to observe the elderly using gadgets freely and booking tourist services independently. To a large extent, the trend of such trips is connected with the development of modern means of communication, mobile applications and rental services, which anyone can use by planning their vacation in advance [10].

2-Picture. Factors affecting the development of independent tourism are reflected.

In the last two decades, tourists have been booking trips independently through online travel agencies. These online companies offer the convenience of booking from home for tourists and often attract travelers with offers such as package deals and discounted rates. As a result, many travelers are abandoning traditional tour agencies and opting for online travel booking options [11]. According to Statista Mobility Market Insights, two-thirds of travel and tourism revenue will come from online sales channels in 2022. Among the leading companies in the market of online travel agencies, Booking Holdings and Expedia are the largest online booking systems in the world. While Booking Holdings' revenue will exceed \$17 billion in 2022 after the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic, Expedia Group's worldwide revenue will be less than \$12 billion, slightly below the result recorded in 2019. Another online booking system that has grown rapidly in recent years is Airbnb, which mainly rents private homes for family or long-term stays. The total value of Airbnb bookings worldwide will be approximately \$63 billion in 2022, which is three times more than in 2017 [12].

The following conclusions can be drawn from the above analysis. Independent travelers, regardless of age, see digital technology as a key enabler. In order to increase the share of sales of tourist services in the country, it is advisable to register more tourist services in these booking systems. According to Uzbektourism.uz, by 2023, the total number of accommodation tools will reach 4,451, and their number in online booking systems will be 3,356. The figure below shows the statistics of registered hotels by city according to the data obtained from online systems (Table 1) [13].

Table 1. Number of hotels listed on electronic booking platforms by city (2023).

№	Cities	Booking.com	Expedia.com	Ostrovok.ru	Hotels.com
1	Tashkent	687	275	378	248
2	Bukhara	282	91	169	100
4	Samarkand	285	115	159	74
5	Khiva	109	36	52	35
6	Ferghana	22	7	10	7
7	Chimyon	6	6	4	2
8	Nukus	19	8	12	8
9	Urgench	16	16	12	35
10	Andijan	1	-	7	1
11	Navoi	19	6	14	6
12	Karshi	-	4	9	4
	Total number	1446	564	826	520

Source: author's development based on information from electronic subscription platforms

Platforms mentioned above are creating great opportunities for independent travelers to organize their own trips. At the same time, tourism organizations are also increasing sales of services through these platforms without any intermediaries. In conclusion, thanks to the development of digital technologies, travelers can get online information about the services they need, save money by purchasing air or railway tickets from the company's systems, book hotels or resorts at low prices, and also manage them. will have opportunities such as direct communication with resident managers. The traveler performs these operations from his destination, and on the other hand, after arriving at his destination, it is necessary to provide him with the opportunity to use the same Internet speed.

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One of the weak points of the country is the low internet speed within the regions and in remote areas, especially in the extreme zones (mountains, deserts, deserts, water areas) that are more frequented by independent travelers. The weakness of the infrastructure is a serious obstacle to the development of the above directions of tourism. Based on this, the main problem of the research determines the need to conduct additional research on the development of convenient infrastructure for independent travelers in the country. In April 2023, SPEEDTEST GLOBAL INDEX conducted a survey of the countries with the highest internet speeds. Uzbekistan ranks 104th out of 190 countries in terms of mobile internet speed, and 89th in terms of Wi-Fi internet access. The Global Speedtest Index measures internet speed over Wi-Fi and mobile connections from mobile applications of millions of people in over 190 countries [14].

Content analysis of comments left by foreign tourists on specialized tourism web pages.

The world-famous website tripadvisor.com has been operating for several years, and through this website, travelers have the opportunity to independently organize their tour routes. At the same time, every independent tourist can leave their comments on this page after completing their trip. Similarly, independent travelers who visited Uzbekistan left comments about the satisfactory and unsatisfactory aspects of the tourism infrastructure.

Table 5. Content analysis of tourism infrastructure in Uzbekistan [16].

Satisfactory	Unsatisfactory
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -reservation of tourist services from the website (OrexCA.com, http://www.stanjourneys.com); - knowledge of the English language of intercity transport drivers; - knowledge of the Tajik, Persian, Russian and less Turkish languages of the local population; - hospitable people; - availability of cheap guides accompanying or guiding the city and places of interest (students, historical country); - relaxation of the visa policy; -the presence of tourist police in tourist centers that ensure the safety of beaches; - a safe country for female independent travelers; - modern and clean cities; - low level of crime; - deliciousness and safety of national dishes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bad condition of the road from Khiva, from Tashkent to Bukhara; - CDs or audio guides translating from a foreign language into Uzbek; - the low level of knowledge of the English language in the local population, in the air, railway, ticket offices in historical buildings, national restaurants and small hotels; - deception of travelers by local residents (taxi drivers most of the international flights arrive at night; - the size of the interval between international flights and domestic flights; - Lack of trees in city centers; - insufficient lighting of roads and streets at night; - shortage of air and railway tickets; shops

Source: Developed by the author based on reviews from independent travelers on their website

Reviews were posted by 18 independent travelers on tripadvisor.com and journalofnomads.com. During their visits to Uzbekistan, they left their comments about the shortcomings and satisfactory aspects as advice for future travelers.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From the above research, we have identified a favorable infrastructure for the category of independent tourism, in conclusion, it can be said that the current state of the country's infrastructure is not sufficiently developed to attract independent travelers. In this study, relying on foreign experience, social, economic, institutional and technical factors in the development of independent tourism were determined. As a comment on the comments left by a small number of independent travelers who visited Uzbekistan on foreign and national websites, the country has a good potential to attract and increase the flow of independent travelers, and with this we can highlight the following trends:

-first of all, it develops financial income and domestic tourism;

- organizations operating in the field of tourism (hotels, airlines, railways, transport companies, restaurants) will have the opportunity to sell their services directly through online platforms without intermediaries.

Within the scope of this scientific research, the independent tourism category, which ensures the sustainable development of the tourism industry in Uzbekistan as a driver, was analyzed, and the following recommendations were developed for the development of this direction:

1. The country's infrastructure is not uniformly developed. It is known that there are historical cities with a large tourist brand in the territory of Uzbekistan - these are the cities of Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva. These regions are the most visited tourist destinations of the country. In addition, these cities have the best infrastructure for tourism, and every year they receive financial support from the government in order to further develop the existing infrastructure. Cultural tourism is mainly developed in these cities. For many years, foreign tourists have been visiting to see historical monuments. But remote areas with great tourist potential are still neglected. For example, it is necessary to organize modern infrastructure in areas such as Todakul Reservoir, Jizzakh, Surkhandarya, Fergana Valley, Zarafshan, Nurota mountain ranges, rural lifestyle, located in Navoi and Bukhara regions.

2. Another factor preventing independent travelers from visiting Uzbekistan is the high price of transport services. Aero tickets constitute the main part of the expenses of the independent traveler. Therefore, it is necessary to offer bonus systems that are aggregated by airline companies to independent travelers. Returning a certain percentage to the tourist as cashback from every next purchased air ticket. Also, to enable travelers to monitor the price dynamics of air tickets in online services. This allows the traveler to book a ticket at a convenient time.

3. Regularly maintain statistics of independent travelers visiting the country and create a national web page. With this, travelers leave their comments on the web page, which allows us to learn about the shortcomings of the areas and fix them in the future.

In conclusion, it is recommended to improve the services suitable for the category of independent tourism, which ensures the sustainable development of tourism as a driver in the regions of Uzbekistan and determines the ways of its development together with related industries. Using the potential of remote areas to the maximum, building infrastructure, filling the revenue part of the budget system, creating additional jobs for local residents and raising the intellect of young people.

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